

Active Learning Workshops Production: Impacts and Benefits for Engineering Students

Arthur R. Costa¹, Emily M. B. Cornelio², Fernanda R. Silva³, Filipe A. Batista¹, Larissa P. C. Santos¹, Marcus J. A. Oliveira¹, Carla M. C. C. Koike⁴, Dianne M. Viana¹

¹Faculty of Technology, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil

²Gama Faculty, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil

³Department of Education, Faculty of Education, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil

⁴Department of Computer Science, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil

Email: arreico@gmail.com, emilly.mbcornelio@gmail.com, fernandarose27@gmail.com, filipe.aziz@gmail.com, larissapsantos@gmail.com, marcus.jesse1@gmail.com, ckoike@unb.br, diannemv@unb.br

Abstract

This article presents an account of the authors' experience on the preparation, implementation, and follow-up of active learning workshops for motivating the learning in robotics. The active learning strategies used range from "flipped classroom" and "guided practice" to "hands-on" and collaborative learning. The target audience of the workshops are undergraduate students that are going to replicate these workshops, under professor's supervision, to high school students, intending to introduce projects in robotics as tools for studies in math and physics. The workshops format is similar to the final desired structure: three days with two of these days committed to learning concepts and skills that will be employed on the third day dedicated to building a robotic car toy. The theme of the first day is "3D Modelling and Printing", with an introduction to modelling using CAD software to prototype a piece. On the second day, the theme approached is "Arduino Programming Workshop". Finally, on the last day, the students consolidate the knowledge gathering the information obtained during the previous workshops to build, program, and test the robotic car toy. The third workshop was applied for testing in two small groups of undergraduate students and the results were obtained for further improvements. In this article, the impact of the workshops on engineering student's education is described. The technical and not technical knowledge and skills reported by the authors include learn how to prepare lesson plans, additional experience in the workshop themes, communication skills improvement, in other words, the author's self-development process is discussed and related to the results of the workshop.

Keywords: Engineering Education; PBL; Hands on activities.

1 Introduction

Educational robotics has been highlighted among Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) teaching-learning techniques. As a multidisciplinary area, robotics requires an organization of tasks ranging from planning to the assembly of the robot and its programming, and therefore, it is necessary for the full construction of a functional robot that amount of knowledge related to mechanical, programming, electronics and electrical engineering be combined to understand how robotics work (Cambuzzi & Souza, 2015). For this reason, when used as a teaching method, robotics can help in the understanding of physical and mathematical concepts and also bring pieces of knowledge about programming and electronics.

Furthermore, because they are attractive, robots instigate the curiosity of students, making them feel motivated to solve problems related to the assembly and programming of the robot. Moreover, depending on the robot used for classes, a robot can hold many electronic components that require different types of codes to work, which makes the use of robots in STEM teaching-learning complex, depending on what the teacher wants to teach, and fun, by allowing the creativity of students decide what the robot can do.

In this context, for even more effective learning, active methodologies can be used in classes. The active learning, differently from traditional teaching methodologies aims to imbue more knowledge in a more dynamic and interactive way, in the form of games, research, debates, among others. According to Felder & Brent (2009, p. 2) "Active learning is anything course-related that all students in a class session are called upon to do other than simply watching, listening and taking notes". The authors reiterate that active learning happens, for example, when students ask a question, propose and discuss a problem, work individually or in

small groups to solve problems and call for other groups to share responses. Felder & Brent (2009) also points out that a teacher is not doing active learning when lectures, asks questions that the same few students always answer, or conduct debates that only a few students show efforts to discuss.

However, implementing a teaching-learning method so different from what both tutors and students are already used to presents a great challenge. Given this, it is evident the importance of the tutor's role in the implementation of active methodologies. Several studies show that the tutor is a fundamental link concerning knowledge management, therefore, the training of tutors must involve several dimensions of learning: interaction, cooperation, cognition, metacognition, and affection (Medeiros & Faria, 2003).

This article discusses the benefits obtained by students involved in the production of three robotics workshops, and the impacts of these benefits on their academic life and future professional life. This study is divided into six sections. In the introduction, we addressed the relevance of the topic to society. In the second section, it is defined as the type of methodology used for this research, and in the third section, there is a literature review of the topic divided into two subtopics about Active Learning and PBL. In the fourth section, we discussed the results of the research explaining the three workshops and also analyze questionnaires sent to all students present in the workshops. In the antepenultimate section, we present conclusions and implications of the workshops for the students in question, and finally, in the last section, we list the bibliography about the topic developed.

2 Research Methodology

This study provides an analysis of the benefits obtained by undergraduate engineering students in the production of three workshops related to robotics that were applied in three days and tested on undergraduate students to train them to gain sufficient knowledge to later act as tutors in the workshops that will be later applied in high schools.

The three workshops are linked, since, the first and second ones are essential to the understanding of the third one. The first workshop, 3D Modelling and Printing, had as its main goal to use CAD software to model a wheel, later used in a robotic car that was assembled in the third workshop. In this first workshop, different manufacturing techniques were approached and finally, the wheel drawing made by the present students in the workshop was printed on a 3D printer. The second workshop, Arduino Programming Workshop, addressed basic questions about programming and electronics using the prototyping board Arduino. Ultimately, the third and last workshop gathered the knowledge obtained in previous workshops for the mounting of a robotic car. In this workshop, the Problem-Based Learning methodology was used, where the students received parts of the robotic car, an Arduino with electronic components and had, in groups of 3 or 4 people, to assemble and program the robotic car themselves so that it could work.

About the production, five students participated in the elaboration of the workshops and acted as tutors, and of these five, two also participated as apprentices in different parts of the workshops. At the end of those, forms were sent to tutors and apprentices to analyze questions about the teaching-learning methodologies used and to get suggestions for improvements for future workshops.

3 Literature Review

In this section, we are going to present, a literature review about the active learning methodologies and their importance in the educational context.

3.1 Active Learning

As highlighted by Prince & Felder (2006), the traditional teaching methods in which the teacher lectures about a topic and then gives students homework is a demotivating and inefficient methodology, since it takes the students to focus only on activities and exams, and not properly on the reasons they must learn what is being taught or how to apply the knowledge acquired in class. Consequently, traditional teaching techniques may be a problem for engineering students who have to learn how to apply theoretical knowledge to solve problems.

According to Berbel (2011), active methodologies use real or simulated experiences to develop new ways of learning to successfully solve problems arising from social practice activities. In this way, the active methodologies aim to learn by practising, with more autonomy by the students and making them protagonists in their learning, using discussions, practical activities in group and examples that bring the subject close to the student's daily life.

Faust & Paulson (1998) while suggesting exercises to increase student's active participation in classes, affirm that active learning develops critical thinking and writing and analysis skills, besides as help hone argumentative skills. The author exposes the flexibility of the active methodologies, showing how to suit it to each student, adapting it to each learning style.

Srinath (2014) reaffirms the importance of using practical examples, as it helps students to understand introduced concepts and visualize their applications. Therefore, examples shall illustrate concepts – making the theory more accessible – and teach how to apply this knowledge in other situations. Demonstrations facilitate to connect theory and practice, not eliminating theory but complementing it.

But though students usually respond positively to the active methods, some of them can show resistance. According to Tharayil et al. (2018), it can be reduced by making simple actions, like walk around the room and talk with students individually or in groups. The instructor must create a comfortable environment for the students to ask and answer questions without feeling intimidated.

Felder & Brent (2009) suggest a variety of strategies in which students can actively learn. One of these strategies is what they call Thinking-aloud pair problem solving (TAPPS). In this case, one of the students must act as an explainer and explain concepts or texts step by step to other students, and these students must question the explainer student when they feel that something has not been well explained or until there are still doubts.

When acting as a tutor a student must study concepts, prepare a class, analyze ways to pass on knowledge and act as an explainer, making the student the protagonist of his learning. In the end, the student has to make the effort to learn very well to be capable to explain what they know and, when asked questions, the tutor must remember what studied and explain in the better way they can to clarify doubts. Therefore, when acting as a tutor a student learns in the preparation of the class and in the class itself, whereas when a student can explain a concept to another person, this student truly understands what studied (Srinath, 2014).

3.2 Project Based Learning – PBL

According to Barbalho (2017), studies related to teaching methodologies have shown that several universities understand that in the area of engineering there should be a concern to use traditional teaching methodologies. Traditional teaching methodologies lead students to focus on memorizing specific contents for tests, directing all their efforts to pass evaluations, which results in students who do not fully understand what they are studying and the possible ways in which this memorized knowledge can be applied.

Engineering students may have problems with traditional teaching methodologies given that one of the skills developed by an engineer must be the ability to apply physics and mathematics to solve problems. One of the active methodologies that can help with the problem described previously is problem-based learning (and also the project-based learning, with the same acronym PBL), that according to Berbel (2011), was introduced in Brazil in medical courses, but has now also been used in other courses.

According to Hmelo-Silve (2004), psychological research and theory suggest that PBL can help students to learn content and thinking strategies. The author affirms that in the PBL methodology the process of learning is student-centred. In it, a complex problem is given but this problem doesn't have a single answer, so the students must work with other students to think strategies to solve the problem. In PBL the teacher must act as a facilitator of the learning process rather than say all the strategies and knowledge needed for solving the problem. Hmelo-Silve (2004) reiterates that the goals of PBL are to help students to develop flexible knowledge, effective problem-solving skills, a self-directed learning (SDL), effective collaboration skills and intrinsic motivation.

Allen, Donham & Bernhardt (2011) also affirm that in PBL students work in groups to solve complex problems, and although this methodology is most of all used in medical education, problem-based learn can influence positively in the integration of new knowledge with an already existing one in the education of undergraduate students. The authors also point out that “faculty members frequently adopt PBL to help students develop lifelong learning skills” (p. 25) which is exercised along the undergraduate course and continues to be exercised along with professional life.

4 Results

In this section, we discuss, details of the workshops and also present a questionnaires analysis that were applicated to the tutors at the end of each workshop.

4.1 3D Modelling and Printing Workshop

The 3D Modelling and Printing workshop was the first one to be realized. In it, the main objective was to teach the students how to model simple parts using a CAD software called *Solidworks*, a computer graphics software that allows the modelling of numerous objects, and finally to present the required steps for 3D printing. To achieve these goals, it was decided that the design made by the students would be a wheel of a robotic car (Figure 2) that would be later assembled by them in the third workshop. Knowing that the workshop was divided into five stages:

1. A quiz with simple questions about simple machines and physical and mathematical concepts, subjects discussed in a material sent to the students the day before the workshop took place. The test was done and accessed by the students through the *Kahoot!* platform;
2. A theoretical exposition about simple machines, gear types, speed reduction, torque and power;
3. A practical activity where the students, with instructions from the tutor, designed in *Solidworks* a wheel of the robotic car;
4. An explanation on how to use the *Solidworks* Toolbox library to design a cylindrical spur gear;
5. A presentation about the different types of manufacturing, that are: subtractive manufacturing such as turning and milling, additive manufacturing and the main 3D printing technologies. In the end, the students could see the printing of the robotic car wheel they drew.

The technological evolution has allowed us today to print 3D objects. In some universities still, there are no specific subjects about 3D printing and therefore the opportunity to know the necessary steps to print an object, from modelling to the calibration of the printer, is important in the training of an engineer in a future where 3D printing will be much more used than it is today. On the figure 1, there is a picture of the car wheel being printed.

The competitiveness of the market requires that companies often seek improvements in product development processes. With this objective, commonly, physical prototypes are used to help in the communication of the teams responsible for these improvements and to minimize failures, and, because they are tested in their real use environment, something that is often not possible to do through digital simulations, physical prototypes are an irreplaceable step in the technological development (Volpato, 2018) (Wiltgen, 2019). For reasons like these, additive manufacturing methods, or commonly called 3D Printing, are processes that must be known by an engineer.

In our university, there are no subjects that approach directly the use of printers for additive manufacturing, and for this reason, the 3D Modelling and Printing workshop has brought benefits to tutors, bringing an additional experience to students who already knew how to handle a printer and knowledge to students who would not have this contact through subjects during their course.

About CAD modelling, besides *Solidworks*, there are many types of CAD software. This type of tool is extremely important for engineers, especially those responsible for creating projects because it allows the modelling of parts and elaborate drawings. In the early semesters of engineering, it is common to learn technical drawing norms with the help of software similar to *Solidworks* and as future engineers, the knowledge of tools of this type is essential for the creation of new projects.

Figure 1. The car wheel being printed.

Figure 2. Students doing the car wheel using Solidworks software.

4.2 Arduino Programming Workshop

On the second day, the workshop consisted of teach Arduino Programming. The workshop started with theoretical explanations using images to help the understanding of the students (Figure 3), for which the projector was used for the slide show and the responsible tutor who developed the topics, explained the contents always bringing examples of real-life to help the understanding of the learners since that is substantial that the Education “contextualize the contents of the curriculum components, identify strategies to present them, represent them, exemplify them, connect and display the requirements, based on the reality of the place and the time in which the learning takes place are located.” (BNCC, 2015, p. 16).

Figure 3. Arduino circuit

The explanations covered the basic concepts of electronics such as electric current, electric voltage, resistance and Ohm’s Law, the operation of some electronic components, such as source, protoboard, resistor, potentiometer, LED, buttons and motors, was also explored computation and programming focusing on the basics of the C language and finally, there was the introduction to Arduino and its basic operation.

Although programming and electronics knowledge is important for engineers, some courses such as mechanical, civil and environmental engineering, do not address more than one or two subjects about these areas. According to the National Curricular Guidelines of the Engineering Undergraduate Course (2019) in force in the Brazilian territory, all engineering course qualifications must include basic Algorithms and Programming contents. However, such programming disciplines given for engineering courses that do not work directly with

the construction of algorithms are not intended to train programmers, but only introduce basic concepts of programming logic and problem-solving through algorithms (Marcussi et al. 2016).

Programming and electronics are important knowledge that all engineers should have. During engineering graduation, students learn how to solve daily problems in different ways and the logic used to program would be of great help in this development. When programming, the problem is understood, a solution is found and a resolution strategy is drawn up, that is, the ability to solve problems is developed.

In the job market, even though it is not required, having knowledge of programming and electronics in the curriculum often helps in hiring and also in the execution of the profession. The technology is disseminated in practically all professions, consequently, the more knowledge related to electronics and programming, the easier it is to optimize the tasks to be done, to correct problems, among others. That way, all engineers would benefit from having at least a little knowledge of programming and electronics.

In this context, the programming workshop with Arduino serves as an incentive for engineering students to seek to understand more about the subject. For those who have not felt encouraged to dedicate time from their undergraduate studies to these topics, the programming workshop with Arduino serves as an introduction that can later help them understand simple programming and electronic problems.

4.3 Knowledge Integration: Car Toy Construction

Finally, the last workshop focused on the assembly and programming of a robotic car (Figure 4). The students were separated in groups of three or four and then they received kits with loose parts of the car, a battery, an Arduino and some electronic components. This workshop required from the students the knowledge already obtained in the two previous workshops, especially the programming and electronics knowledge obtained in the Programming with Arduino workshop. The steps of the workshop were:

1. Assembly of the robotic car;
2. Circuit assembly;
3. Programming the car so that it could move;
4. Try to go through a predetermined circuit.

All activities were conducted using the active PBL methodology. Under no circumstances did the responsible tutors explain what was to be done, but they were there in case there was any problem that needed intervention.

Figure 4. The robotic car assembled by students.

During the production of the workshops there were several modifications to the prototype of the robotic car, which exercised group work and the ability to transmit ideas, in addition to promoting experience in projects. The choice of components led to a better understanding of the characteristics of each actuator used in the prototype (attributes, advantages and disadvantages for each application).

4.4 Questionnaires analysis

After all the three workshops, the tutors had to respond a questionnaire about their impressions and thoughts over their practice to reflect on the strategies and methods adopted by tutors and their role in these practices based on active learning methodologies - flipped class, guided practice, hands-on and, mainly, the so-called PBL (Problem Based Learning).

Regarding the first day, when asked about the use of the active methodologies in the teaching-learning process, we had positive feedbacks emphasizing that such process becomes more efficient and interesting when the students are actively participating.

When comes about the difficulties faced in the class plan realization and the application of it, the didactic aspect and the capacity of adjusting the language were the ones elected, that is, of explaining complex things easily.

Finally, concerning what that experience add as an engineer's students and personally, the answers were: "I learned new things before even studying undergraduate"; "I realized that I have to improve my didactic ability, for the contents be understandable to everyone" and "Being tutor, I could observe details that are going to help me to prepare better workshops in the future". In contrast, aspects that have to be improved were; "Theoretical classes about Physics concepts"; "We need to develop our didactical skill", etc.

In the second workshop, the tutor pointed out that the students were very participative during the application of active methodologies, contemplating one of the active learning characteristics.

"Yes", was the answer when asked: Did you create opportunities to stimulate the autonomous and critic thought of the students? That answer reveals that when the student has autonomy, she/he becomes a proactive individual, able to solve problems more easily, inside and outside the educational context, and learns to be critical about what she/he thinks and produces.

Lastly, the experience added as an engineer's students and personally, become the realization that it is not easy to plan a class and neither put what was planned in practice, even more when the apprentices do not know the subject taught.

The last one workshop, when questioned about the importance of the robotic for education, was mentioned that the Educational Robotics allows that the students develop reasoning, promotes the interaction between student-student and student-tutor, and also motivate the high school's alumni to choose a STEM career. It is important to cite that, the Educational Robotics emerged around 1960, when its pioneer Seymour Paper developed his theory of constructionism and advocated the use of computers in schools as a resource that attracted children (Wildner, 2015) being a powerful tool that is changing the way of teaching.

It is relevant to say that in this specific workshop, the PBL methodology was used, so the tutor considered that did not have any difficulty on planning the class using this resource motivating the robotics learning since the apprentices were very participative and interested in assembling the car toy.

The last item was concerning the experience added and as in the others workshops, the conclusion was that the understanding some teaching methods can help to identify good study methods for tutors themselves who are also students and as future engineers should never stop learning.

5 Conclusion

Given the above, it can be concluded that the active learning workshops were quite productive and successful, even though there were some difficulties encountered during the planning and execution of the same, we managed to achieve our goals.

It is clear that such workshops, with their playful and practical nature, arouse the interest, curiosity and motivation of students in the teaching-learning process and that we, tutors, when we are teaching, we are learning at the same time that we interact with the apprentice, valuing autonomy, stimulating the exchange of knowledge, aspects these, essentials in active learning.

Finally, with the results obtained, the workshops will be improved for later application with high school students and new workshops will be created. It is hoped, therefore, that this work has contributed to the reflection of the theme.

6 References

- Allen, D. E., Donham, R. S. & Bernhardt, S. A. (2011). Problem-Based Learning. *New Directions For Teaching And Learning*. 21-29. doi: 10.1002/tl.465
- Barbalho, S. C. M., Reis, A. C. B., Bitencourt, J. A., Leão, M. C. L. A. & da Silva, G. L. (2017). Project Based Learning approach for Production Planning and Control: analysis of 45 projects developed by students. *Production, São Paulo*, 27, 1-16. doi: 10.1590/0103-6513.225916.
- Berbel, N. A. N. (2011). Active methodologies and the promotion of student autonomy. *Semina: Social Sciences and Humanities*, 32 (1), 25-40. doi: 10.5433/1679-0359.2011v32n1p25.
- BNCC, Ministry of Education (2015). National Common Curriculum Base. *Brasília, MEC*. Available in: <http://basenacionalcomum.mec.gov.br/images/BNCC_EI_EF_110518_-versaofinal_site.pdf>.
- Brazilian Association of Higher Education Maintainers. National Curriculum Guidelines of the Engineering Undergraduate Course. Available in: <https://abmes.org.br/arquivos/legislacoes/Resolucao-CNE-CES-002-2019-04-24.pdf>.
- Cambruzzi, E. & De Souza, R. M. (2015). Educational Robotics in the learning of Programming Logic: Application and Analysis. *IV BRAZILIAN CONGRESS OF INFORMATICS IN EDUCATION, 2015, Maceió. Brazilian Computer Society - SBC*. doi: 10.5753/cbie.wie.2015.21.
- Faust, J. L. & Paulson, D. R. (1998). Active learning in the college classroom. *Journal on Excellence in College Teaching*, 9 (2), 3-24.
- Felder, R. M. & Brent, R. (2009). Active Learning: An Introduction. *ASQ Higher Education Brief*, 2, 1-5.
- Hmelo-Silver, C. E. (2004). Problem-Based Learning: What and How Do Students Learn?. *Educational Psychology Review*, 16(3), 235-266.
- Marcussi, L. D., Guedes, C., Filho, R. G. D. M., Filho, R. M. S. & Junior, C. R. B. (2016). Pesquisa no Ensino de Algoritmos e Programação nas Engenharias: Estudos e Resultados Preliminares. *Symposium of Production Engineering*.
- Medeiros, M. F & Faria, E. T. (2003). Educação a distância: cartografias pulsantes em movimento. *EDIPUCRS*, Porto Alegre.
- Prince, M. J. & Felder, R. M (2006). Inductive Teaching and Learning Methods: Definitions, Comparisons, and Research Bases. *Journal of Engineering Education*. 123-138.
- Srinath, A. (2014). Active Learning Strategies: An illustrative approach to bring out better learning outcomes from Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) students. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 9 (9), 21-25. doi: 10.3991/ijet.v9i9.3979.
- Tharayil, S., Borrego, M., Prince, M., Nguyen, K. A., Shekhar, P., Finelli, C. J. & Waters, C. (2018). Strategies to mitigate student resistance to active learning. *IJ STEM*, 5 (7), 1-16, doi: 10.1186/s40594-018-0102-y.
- Volpato, N. (2018). Manufatura aditiva: tecnologias e aplicações da impressão 3D. *Publisher Edgard Blucher*, 1 ed, 401.
- Wildner, M. C. S. (2015). Robótica Educativa: Um Recurso Para o Estudo de Geometria Plana no 9º Ano do Ensino Fundamental. *Univates University Center, Rio Grande do Sul*.
- Wiltgen, F. (2019). Protótipos e Prototipagem Rápida Aditiva - Sua Importância no Auxílio do Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico. doi: 10.26678/ABCM.COBEP 2019.COF2019-0441.